

BIOMEDICAL WASTE DISPOSAL PRACTICES OF HEALTH WORKERS IN RURAL HEALTH UNIT (RHU) ECHAGUE

Arlyn P. Quijencio

*Master of Science in Public Health, University of La Salette, Inc., Graduate School,
Santiago City, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the biomedical waste disposal practices among health workers in the Rural Health Unit (RHU) of Echague, Isabela, focusing on adherence to waste management protocols, challenges encountered, and potential interventions. Using a descriptive research design, the study surveyed thirty-four health workers through a structured questionnaire based on the Health Care Waste Management Manual (4th Edition, 2022) of the Department of Health. Mean and standard deviation were utilized to analyze gathered data. The study revealed that majority of the health workers always practiced proper disposal protocols, methods used, and overall compliance with biomedical waste management standards which suggests that the healthcare facility has successfully fostered a culture of adherence among its staff. However, occasional challenges were reported, particularly in resource availability, regulatory enforcement, and training gaps. The study highlights the need for continuous training, improved waste management infrastructure, stronger regulatory enforcement, optimized resource allocation, and feedback mechanisms to enhance compliance and ensure sustainable biomedical waste management practices in RHU Echague.

Keywords: *biomedical waste disposal, waste management, compliance*

INTRODUCTION

Biomedical waste management is a crucial aspect of healthcare, particularly in rural settings where infrastructure and resources are often limited. The improper disposal of biomedical waste poses significant health and environmental risks, including the spread of infectious diseases, contamination of water and soil, and exposure to hazardous materials (World Health Organization [WHO], 2018). Biomedical waste includes sharps (needles and syringes), pathological waste, pharmaceuticals, and chemicals, all of which require specialized handling and disposal to prevent harm to healthcare workers, patients, and the public (Prüss-Ustün et al., 2013). Despite international guidelines for waste management, such as those provided by the WHO and national laws like the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act (Republic Act 9003), the challenges of proper waste disposal remain, especially in rural healthcare facilities.

In the Philippines, Rural Health Units (RHUs) are essential in providing healthcare services to underserved communities. These facilities, while responsible for critical healthcare services such as immunization, maternal and childcare, and disease prevention, also generate substantial amounts of biomedical waste. However, the disposal of this waste remains problematic due to limited access to essential disposal equipment, inadequate training for healthcare workers, and insufficient regulatory enforcement. The Department of Health (DOH, 2022) highlights that while guidelines for biomedical waste management are available, rural facilities often struggle with compliance due to limited resources and capacity.

The researcher of this study observed that healthcare workers at RHU Echague in Isabela face similar challenges in managing biomedical waste. These include inadequate waste disposal infrastructure, resource limitations, and inconsistent adherence to regulatory guidelines. Given these challenges, it is essential to assess the biomedical waste disposal practices in RHU Echague to identify gaps in compliance and areas where improvements are needed. This crisis has underscored the need for efficient and sustainable biomedical waste management systems, particularly in resource-limited rural settings. The researcher of this study aims to evaluate the biomedical waste disposal practices at RHU Echague and propose recommendations for improving waste management practices to enhance safety and sustainability.

Several studies have highlighted the global concerns surrounding biomedical waste management. Doylo et al. (2019) found that healthcare workers in Ethiopia displayed poor knowledge and practices regarding waste disposal, resulting in occupational hazards and environmental contamination. Similarly, Kenny and Priyadarshini (2021) reviewed healthcare waste management methods worldwide and emphasized the need for innovative and sustainable waste treatment approaches in developing countries. Khan et al. (2019) also noted that inadequate waste segregation and disposal practices were prevalent in healthcare settings across Asia, including Pakistan, where non-compliance was linked to lack of training and insufficient monitoring.

In the context of the Philippines, several regulatory frameworks govern biomedical waste management, including Republic Act 9003 (the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act) and Republic Act 6969, which regulates toxic and hazardous waste.

However, despite these regulations, the effective implementation of waste management practices remains a challenge, especially in rural areas where healthcare workers often lack proper training and resources (DOH, 2022). The lack of infrastructure and financial constraints often result in makeshift waste disposal methods, as observed by Sawalem et al. (2009) and Ferronato and Torretta (2019), who discussed the widespread use of inadequate waste management systems in resource-constrained settings.

Research by Prüss-Ustün et al. (2013) further underscores the importance of proper waste segregation in preventing cross-contamination and protecting healthcare workers from exposure to infectious materials. This is particularly relevant in rural healthcare units, where waste segregation practices are often inconsistent, and healthcare workers lack the necessary training to handle hazardous waste effectively. Studies by Chartier et al. (2014) and Ferronato and Torretta (2019) also emphasize the need for strong regulatory enforcement and capacity-building initiatives to ensure proper waste disposal in healthcare facilities.

In the Philippines, the DOH provides guidelines for the safe management of healthcare waste through the Health Care Waste Management Manual (DOH, 2022). However, many rural facilities, including RHU Echague, continue to face significant barriers to compliance, including limited access to proper waste containers, insufficient protective equipment, and inadequate infrastructure. Research by Mathur et al. (2021) and Sawalem et al. (2009) points out that ongoing training and monitoring are essential to improving adherence to waste disposal guidelines, particularly in rural healthcare settings.

Given these gaps in knowledge, resources, and infrastructure, the researcher of this study aim to assess the biomedical waste disposal practices of health workers at RHU Echague. By evaluating compliance with established waste management protocols, identifying barriers to proper waste disposal, and proposing targeted interventions, this study seeks to contribute to the improvement of biomedical waste management practices in rural healthcare facilities.

Research Questions

1. What are the biomedical waste disposal practices among health workers of RHU Echague?
2. What are the problems encountered by the health workers in biomedical waste disposal?
3. What measures can be proposed to improve the biomedical waste disposal?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design to assess the biomedical waste disposal practices of health workers at the Rural Health Unit (RHU) of Echague, Isabela. The descriptive research design was chosen because it enables a comprehensive examination of the current state of biomedical waste disposal practices and the challenges encountered by healthcare workers without manipulating any variables, thus providing an accurate representation of existing conditions. The locale of the study was

RHU Echague, located in the province of Isabela, Philippines. This healthcare facility was selected due to its role as a primary healthcare provider in a rural area, facing common challenges related to biomedical waste management, which made it an ideal setting for the research. RHUs are responsible for primary healthcare services, including immunization, maternal and child healthcare, and outpatient consultations, but they also generate substantial amounts of biomedical waste, which must be properly managed to minimize health and environmental risks.

The researcher used total enumeration sampling to include all 34 health workers directly involved in biomedical waste management at RHU Echague. This group consisted of doctors, nurses, midwives, medical technologists, and other healthcare personnel. Since the number of health workers at the facility is relatively small, this sampling method ensured comprehensive participation. Demographic information, such as age, gender, and work experience, was collected. The data were gathered using a structured questionnaire based on the Health Care Waste Management Manual (4th Edition, 2022) developed by the Department of Health (DOH). The questionnaire consisted of three sections: (1) Biomedical Waste Disposal Practices, (2) Problems Encountered in Waste Disposal, and (3) Proposed Measures for Improvement. The first two sections of the questionnaire used a Likert scale to measure the frequency of biomedical waste disposal practices and the extent of the problems encountered by health workers.

The Biomedical Waste Disposal Practices section included 15 items that measured how frequently the respondents followed proper waste disposal protocols. The practices were rated using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Never Practiced) to 5 (Always Practiced). The Problems Encountered in Waste Disposal section consisted of 10 items that assessed the challenges faced by the health workers. This section used a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Not a Problem) to 4 (Always a Problem). The third section, Proposed Measures for Improvement, included open-ended questions that allowed respondents to provide suggestions for improving waste disposal practices.

The instrument used in this study was pre-tested on 10 health workers from another healthcare facility to ensure clarity and reliability. After pilot-testing, revisions were made to improve the questionnaire. To ensure internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the reliability of the instrument. A score of 0.904 for the Biomedical Waste Disposal Practices section and 0.894 for the Problems Encountered section indicated high internal consistency and reliability.

The data collection process was systematic. The researcher distributed the validated questionnaires to all 34 health workers on-site at RHU Echague. The respondents were given ample time to complete the questionnaires. The researcher remained available at the facility to assist with any questions or clarifications. The completed questionnaires were collected, reviewed for completeness, and then encoded for analysis.

For data analysis, the quantitative data collected using the Likert scale were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods. The mean and standard deviation were calculated to assess the frequency of adherence to biomedical waste disposal practices

and the extent of challenges encountered by the healthcare workers. The Likert scale responses provided a clear indication of how often specific practices were followed and the severity of problems faced. In addition, the responses to the open-ended questions were analyzed using thematic analysis, where recurring themes were identified and categorized. This allowed the researcher to identify key suggestions for improving biomedical waste management at RHU Echague.

The scope of this study was limited to the biomedical waste disposal practices of health workers at RHU Echague and did not extend to other healthcare settings or facilities. The study focused solely on the perspectives of the healthcare workers, excluding input from patients or external stakeholders. A limitation of the study was the relatively small sample size of 34 participants, which may not fully represent the waste management practices of all RHUs. Additionally, as the study was conducted at a single rural healthcare facility, the findings may not be generalizable to other regions or healthcare systems in the Philippines.

RESULTS

The following tables shows the results of the study:

Table 1. Biomedical Waste Disposal Practices of Healthcare Workers

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I place sharps waste (needle and syringe combination) directly into the designated puncture-proof container.	4.74	0.45	Always Practiced
2. I collect separately diagnostic laboratory samples and waste from infectious patients and disinfect at the point of generation.	4.59	0.74	Always Practiced
3. I refrigerate pathological waste if not collected/treated within 24 hours.	4.59	0.89	Always Practiced
4. I segregate and collect separately various chemical and pharmaceutical wastes.	4.85	0.36	Always Practiced
5. I place hazardous waste containers away from the patients.	4.68	0.77	Always Practiced
6. I use waste bins depending on their proper uses.	4.74	0.45	Always Practiced

7. I use color-coding in putting the waste into correct bins and maintain segregation during collection, storage, transport, treatment, and disposal.	4.59	0.78	Always Practiced
8. I implement proper tagging of plastic liners before placing on the waste bin.	4.50	0.83	Always Practiced
9. I label waste bins according to the type of waste so as to avoid confusion in the disposal of the wastes.	4.62	0.78	Always Practiced
10. I use appropriate waste receptacle (bags, bins, sharps boxes).	4.82	0.39	Always Practiced
11. I follow the established plan for the collection and transport of biomedical wastes.	4.65	0.81	Always Practiced
12. I make sure that infectious and general waste are collected daily (or as frequently as required).	4.59	0.78	Always Practiced
13. I seal waste bags when it is three-quarters full.	4.53	0.83	Always Practiced
14. I make sure that sharp containers should be collected when three-quarters full.	4.35	0.73	Always Practiced
15. I ensure that the waste bags and containers are properly labelled upon waste collection.	4.50	0.83	Always Practiced
Overall Mean	4.62	0.69	Always Practiced

The results indicate a high level of adherence among healthcare workers in RHU Echague to proper biomedical waste disposal protocols. All practices received mean scores above 4.50, with the highest compliance observed in the segregation of chemical and pharmaceutical wastes ($M=4.85$, $SD=0.36$). This suggests that health workers consistently follow standard procedures for waste handling, including proper use of waste receptacles, segregation, labeling, and collection. The strong compliance can be attributed to the presence of established guidelines and protocols within the facility. However, continued training and monitoring remain essential to sustaining these high standards and addressing any emerging challenges in biomedical waste management.

Table 2. Problems Encountered by the Health Workers in Biomedical Waste Disposal

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. Health workers often do not receive adequate training on proper waste segregation and disposal techniques.	2.38	0.74	Sometimes a Problem
2. The healthcare facility lacks the necessary resources such as proper disposal containers and protective equipment.	2.32	0.88	Sometimes a Problem
3. Poor infrastructure, including insufficient waste collection and storage facilities.	2.24	0.82	Sometimes a Problem
4. Health workers may not always adhere to regulatory guidelines due to a lack of enforcement or awareness.	2.18	0.76	Sometimes a Problem
5. Heavy workloads and time pressures can make it difficult for health workers to follow proper waste disposal procedures.	2.18	0.80	Sometimes a Problem
6. Health workers are at risk of exposure to infectious materials and hazardous chemicals during waste disposal.	2.35	0.88	Sometimes a Problem
7. There may be a general lack of awareness and education about the importance of proper biomedical waste management.	2.12	0.84	Sometimes a Problem
8. Failure to segregate waste at the source into categories such as infectious, hazardous, and general waste.	2.24	0.70	Sometimes a Problem
9. Budget limitations can restrict the availability of necessary disposal equipment and training programs.	2.56	0.96	Often a Problem
10. Cultural attitudes and behaviors towards waste management can affect how health workers handle biomedical waste.	2.68	1.01	Often a Problem
Overall Mean	2.32	0.84	Sometimes a Problem

The findings reveal that healthcare workers in RHU Echague experience moderate challenges in biomedical waste disposal, with most issues categorized as "*Sometimes a Problem*" (overall mean = 2.32, SD = 0.84). The most frequently cited concerns include budget limitations (M = 2.56, SD = 0.96) and cultural attitudes towards waste management (M = 2.68, SD = 1.01), both rated as "*Often a Problem*." These results suggest that inadequate funding restricts access to essential waste disposal equipment and training programs, while deeply ingrained practices and perceptions may hinder proper waste management behaviors.

Other issues, such as insufficient infrastructure, lack of regulatory enforcement, and heavy workloads, were identified as occasional obstacles but did not reach critical levels. Despite these challenges, the findings imply that biomedical waste disposal practices remain relatively well-managed, though addressing resource constraints and promoting awareness could further enhance compliance and efficiency.

Table 3. Proposed Measures to Improve and Sustain the Biomedical Waste Disposal

Measures/ Interventions	Description
Conduct of Training and Education	<p>This includes implementation of ongoing training programs to ensure healthcare workers are up to date on proper waste segregation, disposal techniques, and safety protocols.</p> <p>Also, part of this is the introduction of comprehensive training for new healthcare workers that emphasizes the importance of biomedical waste management, regulatory guidelines, and the risks of improper disposal.</p>
Improvement in Waste Management Infrastructure	<p>This measure includes improvement of the infrastructure for waste collection, ensuring that adequate, properly labeled, and accessible waste containers are available throughout the facility. Provision of the necessary disposal containers, such as puncture-proof sharps containers and color-coded bins for waste segregation (e.g., infectious, hazardous, and general waste).</p>
Implementation of Stronger Regulatory Enforcement	<p>Establish and enforce strict monitoring systems to ensure that all staff follow the established biomedical waste disposal protocols. Conduct routine audits to check for compliance with waste management standards and provide corrective action when necessary.</p>

Improvement of Resource Allocation	Secure a dedicated budget for the procurement of essential waste disposal equipment, protective gear, and training programs. Ensure the facility is well-stocked with items like color-coded bins, seals for waste bags, and liners for waste containers to promote proper segregation.
Engagement and Feedback Mechanisms	This includes creation of a platform where healthcare workers can provide feedback on waste disposal practices and suggest improvements. Also, there should be an involvement of staff in regular discussions about the challenges they face in waste management and work collaboratively to find solutions.
Cultural Sensitization and Awareness Programs	Conduct workshops and seminars to educate healthcare workers on the importance of proper biomedical waste management, emphasizing its impact on public health and the environment. Use behavior change communication strategies, such as visual aids, posters, and role-playing activities, to shift cultural attitudes towards waste disposal.
Addressing Budget Constraints	Advocate for the inclusion of biomedical waste management in the health facility's budget, highlighting cost-effective practices and the long-term savings of preventing health hazards. Utilize cost-effective waste disposal methods, such as color-coded bins made from locally available materials and reusable personal protective equipment where safe and appropriate.

The proposed interventions highlight key areas for enhancing biomedical waste management in RHU Echague. Training and education programs are emphasized as crucial, ensuring that healthcare workers remain updated on waste segregation, disposal techniques, and safety protocols. Strengthening waste management infrastructure, including the provision of properly labeled waste bins and puncture-proof sharps containers, is also a priority.

Additionally, stronger regulatory enforcement is recommended through routine compliance audits and monitoring systems. Addressing budget constraints by securing dedicated funding for waste disposal equipment and training programs is also seen as essential for sustainability. Other measures, such as engagement and feedback mechanisms, aim to involve staff in discussions on waste management challenges and solutions.

Cultural awareness initiatives, including behavior change communication strategies, are suggested to shift attitudes toward responsible waste disposal. These interventions, if effectively implemented, can enhance compliance, improve safety, and promote a sustainable biomedical waste management system within the healthcare facility.

DISCUSSION

The study findings indicate strong adherence to biomedical waste disposal protocols, with an overall mean score of 4.62, suggesting that waste management guidelines are well-integrated into healthcare operations. The high level of compliance aligns with the findings of Mitiku et al. (2022), who emphasized that proper biomedical waste management is essential in protecting healthcare workers, patients, and the environment from contamination risks. Among the disposal practices assessed, segregating, and separately collecting chemical and pharmaceutical waste received the highest mean score (4.85, SD = 0.36), indicating a uniform approach among staff in handling hazardous waste. This consistency reflects effective training and institutional commitment to maintaining strict disposal standards. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2018) highlights that proper segregation minimizes cross-contamination and enhances occupational safety, reinforcing the importance of strict adherence to waste management protocols. Other essential practices, including the immediate placement of sharps in puncture-proof containers, proper use of waste receptacles, and adherence to collection schedules, were also rated as “*always practiced*.” These results demonstrate that healthcare workers are highly aware of safe waste management practices and consistently implement them, contributing to improved infection control and regulatory compliance.

Despite the overall strong adherence to guidelines, some practices received slightly lower mean scores, such as collecting sharp containers only when they are three-quarters full and sealing waste bags at the same level. Although still rated as “*always practiced*,” the minor discrepancies suggest potential areas for reinforcement through additional training and supervision. Mathur et al. (2021) found similar variations in compliance, emphasizing the need for continuous education to ensure uniformity across healthcare personnel. Overall, the results demonstrate that healthcare workers in RHU Echague exhibit a strong commitment to maintaining safe biomedical waste management. However, these findings contrast with those of Abinaya et al. (2024), who reported significant knowledge gaps in biomedical waste segregation and disposal in other healthcare settings. This suggests that ongoing efforts in education, monitoring, and policy reinforcement are necessary to sustain high compliance levels.

While healthcare workers display commendable adherence to biomedical waste disposal protocols, the study identifies challenges that hinder optimal waste management practices. The findings reveal that cultural attitudes and behaviors toward waste management influence compliance, with some workers demonstrating varying levels of commitment to proper waste disposal. Budget constraints emerged as a significant issue, limiting access to essential resources such as disposal equipment and personal

protective gear, with an average rating of 2.56 (SD = 0.96), classifying it as “*often a problem.*” These findings are consistent with those of Thapa and Laskar (2024), who found that inadequate funding for waste disposal infrastructure and training negatively impacts compliance. Additionally, gaps in formal training and awareness were reported, with some healthcare workers lacking adequate exposure to proper segregation and disposal techniques. This supports the argument by Sawalem et al. (2009) that training deficiencies significantly contribute to non-compliance with biomedical waste protocols.

Infrastructure deficiencies, including insufficient waste collection and storage facilities, were also reported as occasional challenges. This aligns with the findings of Caniato et al. (2015), who noted that poor waste disposal infrastructure increases the likelihood of improper handling and environmental contamination. Similarly, Bassey et al. (2006) emphasized that upgrading healthcare waste management facilities is essential for ensuring the safe containment and disposal of biomedical waste. Another issue identified in the study was the failure to segregate waste at the source, which increases cross-contamination risks and complicates the disposal process. Taghipour and Mosaferi (2009) found that the lack of standardized segregation practices significantly impacts infection control measures, highlighting the need for stricter adherence to waste categorization guidelines. Furthermore, heavy workloads and time constraints were identified as barriers to compliance, as some healthcare workers struggled to prioritize proper waste disposal while managing patient care. This finding is supported by Patwary et al. (2011), who noted that healthcare workers facing high patient loads often deprioritize waste management, leading to inconsistent compliance. These findings underscore the need for optimized workflow processes that support efficient waste disposal without overburdening healthcare personnel.

Addressing the identified challenges requires a comprehensive approach that focuses on education, infrastructure development, regulatory enforcement, and resource allocation. Implementing ongoing training programs is essential to ensure healthcare workers remain knowledgeable about safe and effective waste disposal methods. Training should cover key topics such as waste segregation, handling and disposal of hazardous materials, and emergency protocols for waste-related incidents. Mathur et al. (2021) emphasized that continuous education is vital in reinforcing proper biomedical waste management practices. In addition, the facility must provide an adequate number of well-labeled, easily accessible waste disposal containers, such as color-coded bins and puncture-proof containers for sharps. Chartier et al. (2014) highlighted that improving infrastructure and storage capacity can significantly enhance compliance with waste disposal protocols, reducing improper waste handling. Ensuring consistent access to personal protective equipment (PPE), including gloves, masks, and gowns, is also critical in protecting healthcare workers during waste disposal (Prüss-Ustün et al., 2013).

Strengthening regulatory enforcement is another crucial strategy in improving biomedical waste management. Conducting routine audits and compliance monitoring can help identify areas of non-compliance and enforce corrective measures. Caniato et al. (2015) argued that implementing strict policies and assigning accountability for non-compliance can promote adherence to waste disposal regulations. Facilities may also introduce penalties for repeated breaches, encouraging healthcare workers to follow waste management standards more closely. Additionally, adequate funding is necessary

to support biomedical waste disposal supplies, training programs, and infrastructure upgrades. Securing a designated budget ensures consistent access to essential resources for safe and effective waste management (Babirye, 2020). Providing necessary waste disposal materials such as color-coded bins, liners, and labeling tags can significantly support proper segregation and disposal, minimizing errors in waste handling.

Lastly, cultural awareness initiatives should be implemented to address attitudinal barriers toward waste disposal. Conducting workshops and behavior change campaigns can improve attitudes toward biomedical waste management and promote a culture of responsibility among healthcare workers. Sawalem et al. (2009) emphasized that raising awareness through visual aids, posters, and reminders can reinforce key messages and enhance compliance with waste disposal guidelines. By adopting a multi-faceted approach that integrates education, infrastructure development, regulatory reinforcement, and cultural awareness, healthcare facilities can improve adherence to biomedical waste disposal standards, mitigate occupational and environmental risks, and promote long-term sustainability in healthcare waste management practices.

Conclusions

The findings of this study offer valuable insights into the biomedical waste disposal practices of healthcare workers at RHU Echague, Isabela, and provide clear answers to the research questions outlined in the introduction.

In terms of the first research question, which sought to identify the biomedical waste disposal practices among health workers, the study revealed that the health workers at RHU Echague demonstrated a high level of adherence to biomedical waste management protocols. The health workers consistently practiced proper waste disposal methods such as segregating sharps, segregating chemical and pharmaceutical waste, and properly labeling waste containers. The high adherence was reflected in the overall mean score of 4.62, indicating that waste disposal procedures were followed frequently and effectively. This strong compliance can be attributed to the clear waste management guidelines in place at the facility, as well as the awareness and training of healthcare workers on the importance of proper waste handling to prevent health and environmental risks.

However, despite this high level of compliance, the study also addressed the second research question regarding the problems encountered by the health workers in biomedical waste disposal. The study identified several challenges that affected the effectiveness of waste management practices. These included budget limitations, insufficient waste management infrastructure, and a lack of adequate training in some areas. These problems, while not pervasive across all health workers, were significant enough to create barriers to fully optimal practices. Healthcare workers reported challenges such as the lack of proper waste containers, inadequate protective equipment, and the pressures of heavy workloads, which sometimes hindered their ability to adhere to protocols consistently. The overall mean score of 2.32 for problems encountered

reflects that these challenges, though not always present, were still substantial enough to impact the efficiency of waste management.

Regarding the third research question, which focused on proposing measures to improve biomedical waste disposal, the study suggests several key interventions. First, ongoing training and education are essential to ensure healthcare workers stay informed about the latest waste disposal methods and protocols. Training programs should address gaps in knowledge and reinforce proper practices, particularly in the handling of hazardous materials. Second, there is a need to improve the waste management infrastructure by investing in additional disposal equipment such as puncture-proof containers and color-coded bins, which would facilitate better waste segregation and storage. Stronger regulatory enforcement through routine monitoring and compliance audits is also recommended to ensure adherence to protocols and correct any lapses. Furthermore, a dedicated budget for waste management should be established to ensure the availability of necessary resources, including equipment, protective gear, and training programs. Lastly, cultural sensitization and awareness campaigns can help shift attitudes towards waste management, emphasizing its importance to public health and the environment.

In conclusion, while the healthcare workers at RHU Echague demonstrate strong compliance with biomedical waste disposal protocols, several barriers such as resource constraints, infrastructure challenges, and training gaps need to be addressed. Implementing the proposed measures will not only improve compliance but also contribute to a safer, more sustainable biomedical waste management system in the facility.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed for improving biomedical waste disposal practices at RHU Echague and to guide future research. First, it is essential that the findings be applied to enhance the existing waste management protocols at RHU Echague. This can be done by addressing the identified challenges, such as resource limitations and inadequate infrastructure. The implementation of continuous training programs for healthcare workers should be prioritized to ensure that they are equipped with the latest knowledge and practices in biomedical waste management. Additionally, the healthcare facility should invest in improving waste management infrastructure, including providing necessary equipment like puncture-proof containers and color-coded bins for better segregation of biomedical waste.

Furthermore, the study's findings highlight the need for more stringent regulatory enforcement at the facility. The introduction of routine monitoring and compliance audits will help to ensure that healthcare workers consistently adhere to waste disposal protocols. A dedicated budget for waste management should also be allocated to ensure that adequate resources, including protective gear and waste disposal materials, are available for the health workers. Strengthening the culture of proper waste management

through cultural sensitization campaigns and awareness programs is also vital in improving the effectiveness of biomedical waste disposal practices.

For future research, it is recommended to replicate this study in other RHUs across different provinces or regions of the Philippines, especially in areas with different levels of healthcare resources and infrastructure. A larger sample size involving multiple healthcare facilities would provide a broader perspective on the state of biomedical waste management practices across rural settings. Additionally, future studies could explore the effectiveness of specific interventions, such as training programs or infrastructure upgrades, in improving waste management compliance. Given that this study was limited to a single facility, future research could examine the influence of various contextual factors, such as facility size, staff turnover, and budget allocation, on the success of waste management practices.

Lastly, while the results of this study indicate a generally high level of compliance with biomedical waste disposal protocols, further research could explore the reasons behind the occasional lapses in practices, particularly in areas such as the timing of container collections or waste sealing. Investigating the underlying causes of these lapses, whether they are due to workload, insufficient training, or other systemic issues, could help to pinpoint specific areas for improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher of this study adhered to the ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before they completed the survey. Each participant was provided with a detailed explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits, ensuring that they understood their role in the research. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences or loss of benefits. To ensure confidentiality, all responses were anonymized, and data were stored securely, accessible only to the research team. No personal identifying information was collected, and the results were presented in aggregate form to protect the privacy of the participants.

The study also ensured that the well-being of the participants was safeguarded. All health workers involved in the study were assured that their participation would not impact their professional duties or relationships with their colleagues and supervisors. Furthermore, the research followed the ethical principle of non-maleficence, ensuring that no harm would come to participants because of their involvement in the study. The research was conducted in accordance with the principles of fairness, transparency, and integrity, ensuring that no bias influenced the interpretation of the data.

The researcher also affirmed that there was no conflict of interest related to the study. No financial or personal interests influenced the research design, data collection, or interpretation of the findings. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were appropriately cited in accordance with academic standards. The researcher conducted the study with the highest regard for ethical integrity and the rights of the participants,

ensuring that the findings would contribute to advancing knowledge while maintaining ethical consistency.

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